

PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: *In this article, we will see that the prosecution service has a duty to ensure the equality of all citizens before the law and the rule of law, the protection of public interests and the safety of the population, and in what order they are appointed, their powers and responsibilities.*

Keywords: *Prosecutor General, Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, protest, Transport Prosecutor's Office, Institute of Control, Military Prosecutor's Office, Criminalists, Senate of the Oliy Majlis, Verkhovna Rada, Bureau of Enforcement, Appeals, Cassation, State Committees, Combating Economic Crimes department, prophylaxis, operative-search, ruling, decision, session of the Plenum of the Supreme Court, inquiry, Peter I, guardian, supporter of the state prosecution, currency issue, Constitutional status.*

*"The prosecutor's office is a body under the protection of the law.
He is in the construction of the rule of law, a democratic society,
in the implementation of legal reforms plays a decisive role "*

Sh.M.Mirziyoyev

The Prosecutor's Office has a special status in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Our Constitution has a separate chapter for the prosecutor's office, which has been given constitutional status and does not belong to the legislature, the executive or the judiciary. It is the supervisory and special executive body of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Of course, all students are interested in the Prosecutor's Office, so it is natural that they have questions about who the Prosecutor is and what his powers are.

First of all, let's look at the history of the prosecutor's office. It originated in France in the 14th century, then in the United States and England. In Russia, the Institute of Prosecutorial Oversight was established in 1867 on the basis of a draft provisional charter, which was established during the reign of Prosecutor Peter I and later the annexation of Turkestan to Russia. Later, when the Uzbek SSR was formed, the prosecutor's office began to operate on an official basis. Although it has been described as a body that protects the interests of the state and all its citizens, it has largely defended the state, the interests of the ruling classes in that state. Only

thanks to independence has Uzbekistan been able to set up its own prosecutor's office. On August 29, 2001, the Law No. 257 "On the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. The law consists of 7 sections, 4 chapters and 56 articles.

The word procurator is derived from Latin and means "procurare - to take care of." Some people think that the prosecutor involved in the trial is a "critic". However, Article 4 of the Law on Prosecutors states that a prosecutor is merely a supporter of public prosecution of an offender in criminal proceedings.

Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is the only centralized system of prosecutor's offices headed by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Procurator General of the Republic of Uzbekistan and his subordinate procurators shall exercise control over the accurate and uniform implementation of laws in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan are approved by the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Article 119 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan "The term of office of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Prosecutor of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, as well as prosecutors of regions, Tashkent city, districts and cities and equivalent prosecutors shall be five years." marked as. Prosecutors, investigators, inquiry officers and case investigators shall be appointed by the citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan who have a higher legal education, have the necessary professional qualities and are physically fit to perform the duties assigned to them. The prosecutor's office monitored four activities. These include control over the implementation of laws, control over the observance of the rights and freedoms of citizens, control over the implementation of laws by law enforcement agencies and the execution of detainees, prisoners, criminal penalties and other measures of criminal law enforcement. control over the observance of laws at the time.

THE MAIN TASKS OF THE PROSECUTOR'S OFFICE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN:

1. Ensuring the rule of law, strengthening the rule of law, protection of the rights and freedoms of citizens, the legally protected interests of society and the state, the constitutional order of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the prevention and suppression of crime.
2. Monitoring the implementation of laws by ministries, state committees, agencies, citizens' self-government bodies, public associations, enterprises, institutions, organizations, governors and other officials;
3. Monitoring the implementation of laws aimed at ensuring the rights and freedoms of citizens;

4. Monitoring the observance of laws in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, military structures of ministries, state committees and agencies;

5. Control over the implementation of laws by the bodies carrying out operational and search activities, pre-investigation, inquiry, preliminary investigation and coordination of their activities in the fight against crime;

6. Preliminary investigation of crimes;

7. Supporting public prosecution in criminal cases, participating in civil, administrative and economic disputes, protesting against illegal court documents;

8. Control over the implementation of laws aimed at strengthening tax discipline, combating crimes and offenses in the field of taxation, currency, as well as compensation for economic damage to the state;

9. Monitoring the observance of the law in the places of detention of detainees, the execution of criminal penalties and other measures of criminal law;

10. Participation in law-making activities and in raising the legal culture in society.

The system of prosecutor's offices:

1. The Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

2. Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Karakalpakstan;

3. Regional and Tashkent city prosecutor's offices;

4. District and city prosecutor's offices;

5. The Military Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, equated to the regional prosecutor's offices;

6. Territorial military, transport and specialized prosecutor's offices, equated to district prosecutor's offices.

7. The Department for Combating Economic Crimes and the Bureau of Enforcement under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as their local branches, shall function.

Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan

It is the sole coordinating body of the Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Crime Prevention and Crime and the Republican Interdepartmental Commission on Juvenile Affairs. The Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan is accountable to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Orders and other documents of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan (except for documents of an individual nature) that contradict the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall be revoked by a decision of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Powers of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

1. Directs the prosecutor's office and exercises control over their activities.
2. may apply to the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the legislative initiative.
3. Participate in the sessions of the Constitutional Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, submit issues for its consideration and express their views on the issues under consideration.
4. Participates in the sessions of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan, comments on the issues under discussion, makes proposals for the Plenum to provide clarifications on issues related to the application of legislation.
5. Makes proposals to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the approval of the composition of the Board of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.
6. Gives ranks to employees of the prosecutor's office and applies to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a petition for the award of higher ranks.
7. Presents the staff of the prosecutor's office for the state awards of the Republic of Uzbekistan and awards the staff of the prosecutor's office with the badge "Honorary Officer of the Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
8. Issue orders and approve regulations on the structural units of the prosecutor's office.
9. Concludes cooperation agreements with the relevant authorities of foreign countries.

The Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall address to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- On the state of the rule of law and the fight against crime - on a regular basis;
- about serious crimes and emergencies - immediately;
- Provides information on the work done by the prosecutor's office - every six months.

The Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall regularly report to the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on his activities. The Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Karakalpakstan shall be headed by the Prosecutor of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, who shall be appointed and dismissed by the Jogorku Kenesh of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in agreement with the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. is accountable to the Jogorku Kenesh of the Republic of Kazakhstan and the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The regional, Tashkent city prosecutor's offices and equivalent

prosecutor's offices are headed by the relevant prosecutors, who are appointed and dismissed by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These prosecutors shall be subordinate to and accountable to the Procurator-General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The first deputies and deputies of the prosecutors of the regions, the city of Tashkent and their equivalents shall be appointed and dismissed by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Heads of departments and divisions, senior assistants to prosecutors, assistants to prosecutors on internal security shall be appointed and dismissed by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Procurators-criminologists and prosecutors-criminologists shall be appointed and dismissed by prosecutors of regions, Tashkent city and equivalent prosecutors with the consent of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is headed by the Military Prosecutor of the Republic of Uzbekistan, who is the Deputy Prosecutor General.

District and city prosecutor's offices and equivalent prosecutor's offices shall be headed by the relevant prosecutors, who shall be appointed and dismissed by the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These prosecutors are subordinate to and accountable to the higher prosecutor and the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Department for Combating Economic Crimes under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its local branches. The status of the Department is equal to that of the Deputy Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan in terms of remuneration, medical and transport services. Headed by the Head of the Department, who is appointed and dismissed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the recommendation of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Bureau of Enforcement under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its territorial divisions. The status of the Bureau is equal to that of the Deputy Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan in terms of remuneration, medical and transport support, on the recommendation of the Prosecutor General of the Republic of Uzbekistan Director appointed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and dismissed by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The Director of the Bureau is the Chief State Executive of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Powers of the prosecutor in court proceedings.

The prosecutor supports the prosecution in criminal proceedings and participates in the examination of evidence in court, expressing his views on the application of the law. The procurator shall have the right, within the scope of his authority, to demand from the court any case in which the court's verdict, decision,

ruling and decision have entered into force. He shall have the right to appeal against the verdict, decision, ruling and decision of the court within the scope of his authority in accordance with the procedure established by the procedural law. In the event that the protest goes beyond the scope of the prosecutor's authority, he shall appeal to a higher prosecutor with a motion to protest. An appeal, cassation, private, or supervisory protest against a court's judgment, decision, ruling, or decision may be amended, supplemented, or revoked by the prosecutor who filed the protest, as well as by a higher prosecutor, before the trial begins. Procurator's control documents include protests, decisions, petitions, applications and warnings.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

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5. National Database of Legislation.
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